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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**A Case Study****CONJOINED TWIN THORACOPHAGUS- A CASE REPORT**¹Dr. Sheeba Hussain Mendhro, ²Dr. Habiba Sharaf, ³Dr. Urooj Malik¹MBBS, DGO, MS-R-2, Resident in Gynea & Obstetric, Zia-ud-Din Medical University Karachi
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Conjoined twin is the rarest form of twin pregnancy with an incidence of 1 in 50,000 to 1 in 250,000 live birth. There are various types of conjoined twin according to the site of conjunction. Among all types thoracophagus is the most risky and life threatening. A 26 years old lady, presented at 31week of gestation to Gynea & Obstetric emergency unit. Her 3D ultrasound showed monoamniotic, monochorionic conjoined twins mated at chest-thoracophagus. Two heads, spines and 4 lower limbs visualized with a single heart. Pleural effusion seen in the 2nd twin, AFI 20.2cm.

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INTRODUCTION:

Conjoined twin is the rarest form of twin pregnancy. Over all incidence of conjoined twin ranges from 1 in 50,000 to 1 in 250,000 a live birth [1-6]. Conjoined twin results from single fertilized ovum after the 12th day of fertilization [2].

In this study, we present a case of an extremely rare condition that was conjoined twins with thoracophagus and diagnosed in 3rd trimester by ultrasound scanning.

CASE REPORT:

A 26 years old lady, primigravida living at Kemari-Karachi, presented to Gynea & Obstetric department at Zia-Uddin hospital for the 1st time on 26.6.18 at 31+1 week twin pregnancy with ultrasound report showing conjoined twins-thoracophagus.

Gynecological history revealed that her menarche was at the age of 12years. She had regular 28 cycle with moderate flow. She was married since 2years. There was no significant medical or surgical history.

During this pregnancy, she did not follow her gestational status regularly at antenatal care centre. Obstetric examination revealed symphysiofundal height 40cm.

3/D Ultrasound showed monoamniotic, monochorionic conjoined twin at 31.0weeks, both fetuses were joined at chest-Thoracophagus. Two heads & spines visualized, single heart, pleural effusion seen in 2nd twin, lower limbs are 4, AFI 20.2cm.

Poor fetal outcome was discussed with the patient and her family after approaching the multidisciplinary team. As vaginal delivery was unfavorable for this case, after explaining all the risk of postpartum hemorrhage and procedure complication, with informed consent patient underwent caesarian delivery. Through an inverted T shaped incision at lower uterine segment, conjoined twins were delivered with birth weight of 2.4kg & A/S 4/1, 6/5, 6/10. Both were females. Conjoined twins were referred to neonatal intensive care unit.

After the surgery, the patient's hemoglobin level was 10.7g/dl. As the patient Hb level & health status were improved, She was discharged on 3rd post-operative day on antibiotic & multivitamins.

DISCUSSION:

Monochorionic pregnancy with conjoined twin is very uncommon [1]. Its cause is unclear yet but incomplete division of zygote occurs between 13th & 15th day after fertilization [3,4]. There are two theories regarding development of conjoined twins. Fission theory states that fertilized egg splits partially & represent delayed separation of embryonic mass after day 12th of fertilization. Fusion theory states that fertilized egg completely separates and stem cells of one fetus fuse with the similar stems cells of other fetus [2,3,4,5,7]

There are various types of conjoined twin according to the prominent site of conjunction; Abdomen (Omphalopagus), thorax (Thoracophagus), Sacrum (Pyogopagus) Skull (Cephalopagus), Pelvis (Ischiopagus) and back (Rachipagus) [2-5]. Thoracophagus is the most common type 19% [3].

Once conjoined Twin is diagnosed, the type and severity of abnormality can be confirmed with 3dimensional ultrasound, Computed tomography & MRI [2,3,5].

In the present study, diagnosis was made in the 3rd trimester by 3-D ultrasound, after involving of multidisciplinary team that were Pediatrician, Sonologist & Obstetrician, termination of pregnancy is offered to the family because of increased risk of intraoperative maternal morbidity as advanced gestation of conjoined twins. Moreover since there was a single heart & aberrant vessels, surgery to separate the conjoined twin –Thoracophagus was not possible & prognosis was expected to be very poor.

CONCLUSION:

Conjoined twin is a rare condition; in every twin pregnancy clinician should be aware about possibility of conjoined twin. Conjoined twins are associated with high perinatal mortality and maternal morbidity, early diagnosis of conjoined twins helps the parents to decide the termination of pregnancy where prognosis is poor.

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